

Advanced Qualitative Analysis with ATLAS.ti: A Practical Guide to Quantifying Coding Using CAQDAS.

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ABSTRACT

This manual presents a methodological guide for conducting advanced qualitative analysis supported by software using ATLAS.ti within the CAQDAS (Computer-Assisted Qualitative Data Analysis Software) framework. It describes the process of preparing the corpus and configuring the project, including the organization and import of documents derived from interviews, professional narratives and focus groups. The manual highlights the creation and management of codes to categorize information systematically, as well as the use of quotations to identify and link specific segments of text to the relevant analytical categories.

The manual details procedures for exploring the structure of the corpus through frequency analysis and the identification of code co-occurrences, facilitating the detection of thematic patterns within the data. It explains how the results of qualitative coding can be transformed into analytical matrices that relate codes and documents, allowing researchers to examine the distribution of themes across the corpus. Based on these matrices, the manual introduces exploratory data analysis techniques such as contingency tables, chi-square tests, Cramer's V and correspondence analysis.

In addition, the manual describes the export capabilities of ATLAS.ti for generating tables and matrices that can be integrated with other statistical analysis programs, expanding the analytical possibilities of the study. The methodological procedure is illustrated through an applied case study in the field of nursing, demonstrating how the proposed techniques can be implemented in social science research.

This manual provides a structured approach to software-assisted qualitative analysis, to organize large volumes of textual data, identify analytical patterns within the corpus and document each stage of the research process systematically and transparently. The manual is intended for researchers, postgraduate students and professionals interested in advanced qualitative analysis using CAQDAS tools in social science research.

Keywords:

ATLAS.ti, CAQDAS, qualitative data analysis, software-assisted qualitative analysis, mixed methods research, code-document matrix, corpus analysis, correspondence analysis, social science research methods, quantification of qualitative data.

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1. Introduction

Qualitative analysis (Boté-Vericad 2026b) constitutes one of the most widely used methodological strategies in the social sciences for studying complex phenomena through discourse, experiences, and social practices. Unlike quantitative approaches, which are primarily focused on measuring variables and achieving statistical generalisation, qualitative research seeks to understand how individuals interpret their reality and how specific meanings are constructed within particular social contexts.

Among the most common procedures in qualitative analysis are thematic coding (Braun & Clarke 2006), content analysis (Cáceres 2008; Krippendorff 2019), and discourse analysis (Gee 2025; Sayago 2014; Santander 2011). These approaches share a central element: the identification of analytical categories that enable the organisation of textual corpora and the detection of meaningful patterns in the data. In this context, coding represents the fundamental process through which researchers assign conceptual labels to segments of text in order to structure information and facilitate interpretation. Several studies (Miles, Huberman and Saldaña 2020; Mayring 2014) emphasise that coding helps reduce the complexity of the corpus, compare cases, and develop analytical interpretations.

In recent decades, the development of computational tools has expanded the possibilities of qualitative analysis. Software packages known as Computer-Assisted Qualitative Data Analysis Software (CAQDAS), including ATLAS.ti (Lopezosa, Codina and Boté-Vericad 2023; Boté-Vericad and Lopezosa 2024), NVivo (Lopezosa 2020), and MAXQDA (Schueller, Trentin and Hueber 2026; Freitas et al. 2017), enable the management of large volumes of textual data, the organisation of coding systems, and the systematic retrieval of data segments. These tools contribute to structuring the analytical process and documenting the methodological decisions adopted during the research (Silver and Lewins 2014). However, they should be understood as supporting tools rather than substitutes for analytical reasoning (Gibbs 2018).

One of the most relevant methodological debates in contemporary qualitative research concerns the integration of qualitative and quantitative strategies within the same research process. The mixed methods paradigm proposes combining different types of

data and analytical techniques in order to achieve a more comprehensive understanding of social phenomena (Boté-Vericad 2023; Creswell and Plano Clark 2018). Within this framework, some researchers have explored the possibility of quantifying certain aspects of qualitative analysis, particularly when the data have been previously coded.

Beyond association tests, some exploratory multivariate techniques allow researchers to visualise the internal structure of the corpus. Correspondence analysis, for instance, enables the graphical representation of relationships between documents and categories based on a data matrix (Greenacre 2017).

Despite these methodological possibilities, the literature shows that there are still few guides that describe in an integrated manner the full process linking qualitative coding with the structural analysis of the corpus. Many manuals focus either on coding or on the use of qualitative software (Lopezosa 2020; Lopezosa, Codina and Freixa 2022), while quantitative techniques are usually addressed in different methodological contexts (Neuendorf 2017; Krippendorff 2019). As a result, researchers interested in exploring the structure of qualitative corpora often need to combine tools from different methodological traditions.

1.1 Objective and Structure of the Manual

The objective of this manual is to provide an applied methodological guide that enables the integration of these stages within a coherent procedure. In particular, it aims to demonstrate how qualitative coding can be transformed into analytical structures that allow the exploration of discursive patterns through exploratory quantitative techniques.

To illustrate this procedure, the manual employs an applied case study based on professional discourses collected through micro-interviews, professional narratives, and a focus group within the field of nursing. The study of professional experience in healthcare contexts constitutes a relevant area of interest for the social sciences, as it enables the analysis of issues related to work organisation, the emotional experience of care, and institutional dynamics within health systems. In this sense, the case presented in this manual should be understood as a methodological example that can be applied to

different social research contexts. Figure 1 presents the workflow of qualitative corpus analysis.

Figure 1. Workflow of qualitative corpus analysis

The analytical procedure presented throughout the manual, as illustrated in Figure 1, follows a clear sequence, structured as follows:

1. The process of coding the data and constructing the system of analytical categories.
2. The analysis of the distribution of codes within the corpus and the relationships between categories through frequencies and co-occurrences.
3. The transformation of coding into analytical matrices, which enables the application of exploratory statistical techniques.
4. The integration of these results with the qualitative interpretation of the corpus.

The manual proposes an approach that connects three dimensions of qualitative analysis: discourse interpretation, the systematisation of the analytical process, and the structural exploration of the corpus. This approach can be understood as a model of structural discourse analysis, integrating qualitative interpretation of the corpus, descriptive exploration of coded data, and structural analysis of the relationships between analytical categories. The analytical procedure presented combines qualitative discourse interpretation with exploratory quantitative techniques, situating it within mixed methods research approaches applied to textual corpus analysis. This combination allows data to be examined from multiple perspectives and facilitates the identification of analytical patterns within the analyzed texts.

2. Literature Review

This section reviews the literature on qualitative analysis and the subsequent quantification of qualitative data. Although there is extensive literature on qualitative analysis itself, this serves as the starting point for subsequently addressing the quantification derived from coding.

Qualitative analysis constitutes one of the most relevant methodological strategies in the social sciences for understanding complex phenomena through the systematic study of discourse, experiences, and social practices. Traditionally, this approach has focused on the contextualised interpretation of textual data obtained through interviews, focus groups, observations, or documents. However, in recent decades, there has been a growing concern with systematising analytical procedures and ensuring methodological transparency in qualitative research (Miles, Huberman and Saldaña 2020; Nowell et al. 2017; Tracy 2010).

One of the key pillars of this systematisation is coding, understood as the process through which textual data are organised into analytical categories that enable the identification of patterns and recurring meanings. Saldaña (2025) and Mayring (2014) describe coding as an iterative process through which researchers assign conceptual labels to data segments in order to construct theoretical interpretations. Similarly, Miles, Huberman and Saldaña (2020) emphasise that coding reduces the complexity of the corpus and facilitates the identification of analytical patterns. From this perspective, codes function as intermediate units between empirical discourse and theoretical conceptualisation.

The development of qualitative analysis has been closely linked to the emergence of computational tools known as Computer-Assisted Qualitative Data Analysis Software (CAQDAS). Programmes such as ATLAS.ti, NVivo, Taguette or MAXQDA enable the management of large volumes of textual data and facilitate tasks such as coding, fragment retrieval, and the visualisation of relationships between categories. The primary value of these programmes lies not only in their technical capabilities but also in their potential to support complex and transparent analytical processes (Silver and Lewins 2014).

Furthermore, Friese (2019) highlights that qualitative software contributes to structuring analysis and documenting the methodological decisions adopted during research.

However, several studies have pointed out that the use of software does not replace methodological reflection or qualitative interpretation (Gibbs 2018). Similarly, Kuckartz (2014) argues that the value of qualitative analysis fundamentally depends on the coherence of the coding system and the clarity of the research questions.

A well-established tradition within qualitative analysis is content analysis, which seeks to identify conceptual categories through the systematic classification of data. Krippendorff (2019) defines content analysis as a research technique aimed at producing valid and replicable inferences from texts. This approach has contributed to introducing criteria of reliability and replicability into qualitative analysis, particularly through procedures designed to assess intercoder agreement. In this context, Krippendorff's alpha coefficient has become one of the most widely used measures to evaluate the consistency of coding systems. Applications of this measure can be found in various studies (Boté-Vericad et al. 2026; Boté-Vericad et al. 2024; Guallar et al. 2025; Santos-Hermosa and Boté-Vericad 2024; Villarroya and Boté-Vericad 2023).

In parallel with the development of qualitative analysis, recent decades have witnessed the emergence of methodological approaches aimed at integrating qualitative and quantitative methods. The mixed methods paradigm proposes combining different analytical strategies to leverage the strengths of each approach (Creswell 2015, p. 38; Flick 2017; López-Fernández and Molina-Azorín 2011; Suleman and Hopper 2015). Creswell and Plano Clark (2018) argue that the integration of methods allows complex phenomena to be addressed from multiple perspectives, thereby increasing the robustness of findings. Within this framework, some researchers have explored the possibility of transforming qualitative data into quantifiable variables, a process known as quantitising (Love and Corr 2021; Nzabonimpa 2019; Onwuegbuzie 2025; Van Grootel et al. 2020).

The quantification of qualitative analysis is not an entirely new idea. Several authors argue that identifying frequencies and patterns in qualitative data can provide a structural view of the corpus, provided that contextualised interpretation is maintained (Krippendorff

2019; Neuendorf 2017; Nowell et al. 2017). In this line, some authors have proposed using data matrices derived from coding to examine relationships between categories or between documents. Miles, Huberman and Saldaña (2020) and Saldaña (2025) suggest the use of analytical matrices as tools for exploring relationships between qualitative variables.

Another line of research has explored the use of exploratory statistical techniques applied to coded qualitative data. For instance, correspondence analysis allows the visualisation of relationships between categories and documents based on contingency matrices. This method, originally developed by Benzécri, has been widely used to analyse lexical tables and explore the semantic structure of textual corpora (Benzécri 1973; Lebart, Salem and Berry 1998; Costa et al. 2013; Greenacre 2017). Such techniques have been employed in various studies to identify thematic structures in textual corpora, although their application remains relatively limited in qualitative research.

Despite these advances, the methodological literature shows that there are still few systematic guides explaining in an integrated manner how to move from qualitative coding to structural corpus analysis. Most manuals focus on qualitative interpretation or on the use of software such as ATLAS.ti, but devote less attention to the transformation of coded data into analytical structures suitable for quantitative exploration. In this regard, the development of procedures that connect qualitative coding with structural analysis techniques represents a significant contribution to research in the social sciences.

The literature reveals three major methodological traditions related to the analysis of qualitative data. The first focuses on discourse interpretation and the construction of analytical categories (Saldaña 2025; Gibbs 2018; Kuckartz 2014). The second seeks to systematise analysis through replicable procedures, such as content analysis and intercoder reliability assessment (Krippendorff 2019). Finally, a third emerging line explores the integration of qualitative analysis with exploratory quantitative techniques, particularly within the framework of mixed methods (Creswell and Plano Clark 2018; Nowell et al. 2017).

This manual is situated at the intersection of these three traditions. Its objective is to demonstrate how qualitative coding can become the basis for a structural analysis of the corpus that combines qualitative interpretation with the quantitative exploration of discursive patterns.

3. Study Design and Corpus Construction

Qualitative analysis requires a precise definition of the type of data to be analysed, the context of production, and the unit of analysis. These methodological decisions condition the entire subsequent analytical process, as they determine how results are interpreted and what types of comparisons can be made across the data.

In the social sciences, qualitative corpora are typically composed of different types of textual materials, such as interviews, focus groups, professional narratives, institutional documents, field diaries, or observational records, each characterised by distinct conditions of discursive production (Boté-Vericad 2026c; Villarroya and Boté-Vericad 2023). Each of these materials provides complementary perspectives on the phenomenon under study.

3.1. Types of Materials Analysed

For the development of examples, three different types of materials have been used, all of which share the same codebook: micro-interviews, professional practice narratives, and a focus group with a reduced textual corpus.

Micro-interviews consist of brief narratives in which nursing professionals describe their everyday experience in different care contexts. This type of text makes it possible to explore individual perceptions on issues such as work organisation, workload, or relationships with patients and professional teams. In the case of this manual, these materials constitute a sample corpus.

Professional practice narratives describe specific situations that have occurred during healthcare work. Unlike interviews, these texts focus on particular episodes and allow for the analysis of how certain situations are managed within the institutional context.

The corpus also includes a focus group, in which several participants collectively discuss aspects related to their professional practice. This type of material is particularly useful for analysing how certain themes are constructed through interaction between participants and how interpretations of everyday work are negotiated.

From a methodological perspective, the combination of different types of texts allows for comparison of how specific themes emerge across different discursive contexts. For instance, some themes may appear more clearly in individual narratives, while others are primarily articulated in group interaction settings. Accordingly, the texts used for the methodological explanation in this manual are provided in the appendix.

3.2. Unit of Analysis

Before initiating the coding process, it is necessary to clearly define the unit of analysis to be used throughout the study (Grünbaum 2007; Huddleston et al. 2022). In this manual, two analytical levels are distinguished. First, the basic unit of coding: the text segment, that is, the portion of discourse to which a code is assigned during qualitative analysis. Second, for certain structural analyses, the complete document is used as the unit of comparison, allowing the examination of the distribution of codes across different texts. This distinction is important because some analyses are based on the number of coded segments, while others examine the presence or absence of specific themes within each document. The choice of unit of analysis directly influences the interpretation of the results.

Before starting the coding process, it is essential to understand the type of texts that make up the corpus and to situate the coding system within that context. A preliminary reading of the documents allows researchers to identify the type of discourse being analysed and the themes that may appear recurrently. If it is not clear what has been coded and in which context the categories appear, tables and numerical results lose a significant part of their meaning. This will affect subsequent analyses based on frequencies or matrices.

For this reason, it is useful to formulate a set of initial questions during the reading of the corpus. Based on the texts provided in the appendix, it is helpful to consider questions such as:

- Which themes appear most frequently?
- In which texts are tensions or conflicts most evident?

— Which situations are associated with the emergence of elements such as stress or workload?

This preliminary interpretative exercise facilitates the subsequent understanding of the tables and analyses that will be conducted in later stages.

Once the corpus and the unit of analysis have been defined, the next step is to prepare the texts for analysis using qualitative software. This process includes organising the documents, creating the project in ATLAS.ti, and importing the materials that will constitute the corpus. From this point onwards, the qualitative coding process begins, forming the foundation of all subsequent analysis.

4. Qualitative Coding and the Development of the Coding Framework

4.1. What is Coding

Coding constitutes the core of qualitative analysis. Through this process, the researcher assigns analytical categories to segments of text in order to organise the corpus and facilitate the identification of patterns within the data. Coding enables the transformation of complex textual materials into an analytical structure that can be examined systematically. Numerous studies agree that coding represents the first step in reducing the complexity of the corpus. Through this process, textual material can be structured into analytical categories that support systematic interpretation and enable comparison across cases (Braun and Clarke 2006; Mayring 2014; Miles, Huberman and Saldaña 2020; Saldaña 2025).

It is important to emphasise that coding does not simply consist of marking fragments of text. Coding involves identifying relevant dimensions of the phenomenon under study and representing them through analytical categories. In this sense, codes should be understood as analytical tools that allow the organisation of information and guide the interpretation of the corpus. Coding is applied to units of meaning that are defined interpretatively during the analytical process, enabling the segmentation of the corpus according to thematic and discursive criteria.

4.2. Types of Codes

In practice, codes may take different forms depending on the methodological approach employed. Saldaña (2025) distinguishes several types of codes, among which the following are particularly relevant:

- **Descriptive codes:** identify explicit themes or content within the text.
- **Analytical codes:** represent more abstract interpretations of the phenomenon under study.
- **Conceptual codes:** link empirical data with theoretical categories.

In exploratory studies, it is common to begin with descriptive codes and subsequently refine the system of categories as the analysis progresses.

4.3. Construction of the Coding System

A fundamental aspect of qualitative analysis consists in constructing a coding system that is both coherent and analytically useful. This system can be developed in different ways:

- **Deductive approach**, when codes are derived from existing theories or prior research.
- **Inductive approach**, when categories emerge directly from the data.
- **Hybrid approach**, which combines both strategies.

In many qualitative studies, a hybrid strategy is employed, starting from a set of initial concepts that are progressively refined during the analysis of the corpus. In the example presented in this manual, the coding system is organised around four major analytical dimensions related to professional experience in the healthcare context, as illustrated in Figure 2. These dimensions reflect broad thematic areas within professional discourse:

- **Professional context**, including references to the work environment or type of healthcare service.
- **Practice and work organisation**, covering aspects related to workload, time management, and coordination among professionals.
- **Emotional dimension**, including experiences such as stress, frustration, or professional motivation.
- **Institutional relationship**, grouping references to resources, organisational support, or professional recognition.

Figure 2. Analytical dimensions of the sample texts

These code families allow the corpus to be structured and facilitate comparison across different documents, as shown in Figure 2 in ATLAS.ti. These dimensions can be organised in ATLAS.ti through code groups.

4.4. Criteria for an Operational Coding System

For a coding system to be effective in subsequent analysis, it must meet certain methodological criteria. Various authors indicate that coding systems should be conceptually clear, consistently applied, and analytically relevant to the research objectives (Miles, Huberman and Saldaña 2020; Mayring 2014; Saldaña 2025; Gibbs 2018). Among the most important criteria are the following:

- **Conceptual clarity.** Each code should represent a clearly defined idea.
- **Comparability.** Codes should be applicable consistently across different documents.
- **Internal coherence.** The coding system should avoid conceptual overlap between categories.
- **Analytical relevance.** Codes should be directly linked to the research objectives.

A well-constructed coding system facilitates the organisation of the corpus, enables comparison across documents, and supports the identification of thematic patterns.

4.5. Common Errors in Coding

During the coding process, it is common to encounter certain issues that may hinder subsequent analysis. Among the most frequent errors are the following:

- **Overly general codes:** These do not allow for distinguishing between different dimensions of the phenomenon.
- **Redundant codes:** These represent very similar ideas and generate analytical confusion. This issue is particularly common in large corpora.
- **Non-operational codes:** These are difficult to apply consistently across different text segments.
- **Overly specific codes:** These appear in only one or two cases and hinder comparison across documents.

To avoid these problems, it is advisable to review the coding system and make adjustments whenever necessary, periodically.

4.6. Application for Coding in ATLAS.ti

Once the coding system has been defined, the next step is to apply the coding to the corpus using qualitative data analysis software. The general procedure in ATLAS.ti can be summarised in the following stages:

1. Create a new project and import the documents that will form part of the corpus.
2. Define the coding system within the project.
3. Read each document, identifying fragments relevant to the analysis.
4. Assign one or more codes to each selected text segment.
5. Review the coding to ensure consistency in the application of codes.

It is important to note that a single fragment may receive multiple codes if it addresses different dimensions of the phenomenon under study. This type of multiple coding enables the subsequent exploration of relationships between categories through co-occurrence analysis. Coding does not constitute the final objective of qualitative analysis. Its primary function is to prepare the data for subsequent stages of analysis. Once the corpus has been coded, it becomes possible to examine the distribution of codes, identify recurring themes, and explore relationships between categories. This stage marks the transition towards more advanced analyses, such as frequencies, co-occurrences, or code–document matrices.

5. Initial Exploration of the Corpus: Frequencies and Coding Density

Once the coding process is complete, the next step is to explore the overall structure of the corpus. This stage has a descriptive character and allows for the identification of initial patterns in the data before applying more complex analyses. At this stage, the objective is not yet to interpret the discourse in depth, but rather to understand how codes are distributed across the corpus.

In ATLAS.ti (as well as in NVivo or MAXQDA), this exploration typically begins with the analysis of code frequencies and coding density. These indicators provide an initial overview of the most recurrent themes in the data and help guide subsequent analysis.

5.1 Frequencies of Quotations

Frequency analysis consists of examining how many times a given code appears in the corpus. In practical terms, this involves counting the number of text segments to which a specific code has been assigned. This type of analysis makes it possible to identify themes that occur more or less frequently within the discourse. However, these results must be interpreted with caution. Nowell et al. (2017) note that the frequency of occurrence of a theme should not be automatically interpreted as an indicator of its conceptual importance. Some themes may appear infrequently yet hold significant analytical relevance.

For this reason, frequency analysis should be considered an exploratory tool aimed at guiding the interpretation of the corpus. To perform frequency analysis in ATLAS.ti, the **Code Manager** must be opened and the export option selected (Figure 3).

Figure 3. Export of corpus frequencies

Once exported, the generated file—typically in a Microsoft Excel spreadsheet—displays a distribution similar to that shown in the examples in Figure 4. The term *grounded*, specific to ATLAS.ti (ATLAS.ti, 2023), corresponds to frequency.

Figure 4. Frequencies obtained from coding

A	B	C
Code	Grounded	Code Groups
● Emotional exhaustion	4	Emotional dimension
● Healthcare setting	3	Professional context
● Lack of resources	3	Institutional relationship
● Coordination / teamwork	2	Practice and work organisation
● Decision-making	2	Practice and work organisation
● Frustration	2	Emotional dimension
● Emotional stress	1	Emotional dimension
● Institutional communication	1	Institutional relationship
● Institutional support	1	Institutional relationship
● Service organisation	1	Practice and work organisation
● Workload burden	1	Practice and work organisation
● Professional experience	0	Professional context
● Professional motivation	0	Emotional dimension
● Professional recognition	0	Institutional relationship
● Time management	0	Practice and work organisation

5.2. Frequency by Segments and Frequency by Documents

In qualitative analysis, it is important to distinguish between two types of frequency, which can be measured in complementary ways:

1. **Frequency of coded segments**, which indicates how many times a theme appears within the corpus.
2. **Frequency by document**, which indicates how many documents a given code appears.

This distinction is relevant because both indicators provide complementary information. Segment frequency makes it possible to identify recurrent themes in the discourse, whereas document frequency allows for the examination of how themes are distributed across different texts. For example, a code may appear many times within a single document while being absent from the rest of the corpus. In such a case, the total frequency would be high, but the distribution of the theme would be limited.

5.3. Coding Density

Another useful indicator at this stage is coding density. Coding density refers to the number of different codes present within a given document. This indicator makes it possible to identify documents that exhibit greater thematic variety or higher discursive complexity (Boté-Vericad 2026a; Miles, Huberman and Saldaña 2020; Saldaña 2025). For example, a document containing many different codes may reflect a more complex experience or address multiple dimensions of the phenomenon under study. Conversely, a document with few codes may focus on a single specific theme or reflect a less complex narrative.

The analysis of coding density allows for comparison across documents and helps detect potential differences in the thematic or discursive structure of the corpus. The methodological literature on qualitative analysis has highlighted that both the frequency and distribution of codes can be used to identify patterns and compare data segments within the corpus (Saldaña 2025; Kuckartz 2014).

In this context, it is important to distinguish between the frequency of coded segments and the code's presence across documents, as both indicators provide different insights into the organisation of the corpus:

Frequency of segments indicates how many times a code appears across different segments of the corpus. This indicator helps identify themes that occur with greater intensity or recurrence in discourse.

Presence of codes in documents refers to whether a given code appears or does not appear in each document. This indicator allows for the analysis of how themes are distributed across the different texts in the corpus.

The combination of these indicators facilitates an initial exploration of the thematic structure of the corpus and helps guide more detailed subsequent interpretations.

5.4. Interpretation of Descriptive Results

The results obtained through frequency analysis and coding density should be interpreted as an initial approximation to the corpus. This stage makes it possible to address questions such as the following, as introduced in Section 5.1:

- Which themes appear most frequently in the corpus?
- Which codes are most widely distributed across documents?
- Are there documents that are particularly dense from a thematic perspective?

These questions help guide subsequent analysis and identify potential areas of interest within the corpus. However, it is important to remember that these indicators do not yet provide an explanation of the phenomena under study. Their primary function is to offer a descriptive overview of the corpus that facilitates the identification of initial patterns.

5.5. Comparison of Codes Across Groups of Documents

In some cases, it may be of interest for the researcher to conduct comparisons between different groups. To this end, the analysed texts can be grouped according to specific characteristics, such as participants' profiles, type of discipline, or institutional context.

This process allows for the comparison of code frequencies across different groups and facilitates the observation of differences in the structure of discourse. In the case of the example data used in this manual, a comparison has been conducted between primary care and hospital units. An example can be found in Figure 5, which presents an extract from a table (Boté-Vericad 2021).

Figure 5. Extract from the article (Boté-Vericad 2021)

Professor's ($N = 29$) facing barriers on distance teaching: data comparison between Engineering and Science ($n = 11$) and Humanities and Social Sciences ($n = 18$)

Themes and subthemes	Engineering and Science $n = 11$		Humanities and Social Sciences $n = 18$	
	Quotations	%	Quotations	%
Educational material delivery	75	40.32%	79	33.33%
Quality of educational videos	1	1.33%	2	2.53%
Teaching with SNS	1	1.33%	1	1.27%
Technical issues	19	25.33%	19	24.05%
Availability of university resources	44	58.67%	38	48.10%
Future production of educational videos	10	13.33%	19	24.05%
Professors and distance teaching	111	59.67%	158	66.67%
Teaching methodology	21	18.92%	51	32.28%
Additional working hours	6	5.40%	4	3.18%
Professors' reactions	10	9.01%	10	7.94%
Professors' satisfaction in creating videos or live sessions	42	37.84%	44	34.92%
Professors' training	25	22.52%	32	20.25%
Students' attitudes and implications on teaching methodologies	7	6.31%	17	10.76%

To carry out comparisons between groups in ATLAS.ti, the following procedure can be applied:

- 1) Access the option Analyze / Code-Document Analysis.

- 2) Depending on how the data are organised, select the relevant codes for one document and export them to Excel. The same procedure is then repeated for the

remaining documents. In the example, *Microinterview_1* corresponds to a hospital unit, while *Microinterview_2* and *Microinterview_3* correspond to primary care.

Figure 6. Selection of all codes for one document

Once the data have been selected, they are exported to Excel.

In the second step, the same operation is performed for the remaining documents and codes.

Figure 7. Step 2 of grouping by document groups

The selected information is again exported to Excel.

At this stage, two Excel files are obtained, which must be combined, taking into account the codes and their frequencies. Different types of frequency tables can then be constructed. The first option is to create a comprehensive table displaying all codes, their frequencies, and the corresponding percentages. Percentages should be calculated within the spreadsheet.

Table 1. Frequencies and percentages by groups of documents

	Primary Care	Percentage	Hospital Unit	Percentage
● Healthcare setting	0	0%	0	0%
● Workload burden	0	0%	2	18%
● Emotional exhaustion	1	6%	1	9%
● Institutional communication	0	0%	1	9%
● Coordination / teamwork	1	6%	1	9%
● Emotional stress	2	13%	2	18%
● Professional experience	0	0%	0	0%
● Lack of resources	2	13%	1	9%
● Frustration	0	0%	1	9%
● Time management	3	19%	1	9%
● Professional motivation	2	13%	1	9%
● Service organisation	3	19%	0	0%
● Professional recognition	0	0%	0	0%
● Institutional support	0	0%	0	0%
● Decision-making	2	13%	0	0%
Totals	16	100%	11	100%

A second option, particularly useful when dealing with a large number of codes, is to construct a more compact table by grouping related codes as is shown in Table 2.

Table 2. Aggregated frequencies and percentages

Grouped Code	Primary Care	%	Hospital Unit	%
Emotional stress	4	20%	8	33%
Time management	7	35%	6	25%
Workload	2	10%	5	21%
Lack of resources	5	25%	3	13%
Teamwork	2	10%	2	8%
Totals	20	100%	24	100%

Once the distribution of codes across the corpus has been examined, the next step consists of exploring the relationships between analytical categories. In qualitative analysis, these relationships can be examined through the study of code co-occurrences, that is, the identification of situations in which different categories appear together within the same text segment. Co-occurrence analysis makes it possible to detect thematic connections within the discourse and constitutes an intermediate step between descriptive exploration of the corpus and the structural analysis of the data.

6. Co-occurrence Analysis: Identification of Thematic Relationships

Following the initial exploration of the corpus through frequency and coding density analyses, the next step consists of examining the relationships between codes. In qualitative analysis, these relationships can be explored through the study of co-occurrences, that is, the identification of situations in which two or more codes appear together within the same segment of text.

Whereas frequency analysis shows the individual presence of themes, co-occurrence analysis allows for the examination of how these themes are combined within the discourse.

6.1. What is a Co-occurrence

A co-occurrence occurs when two codes are applied to the same segment of text or to segments that partially overlap (Figure 8). This type of overlap indicates that the themes represented by these codes are related within the discourse.

Figure 8. Example of co-occurrence

For example, in a corpus on professional experience in nursing, a text segment might simultaneously receive the codes *workload* and *emotional stress*. In this case, the co-occurrence suggests that both themes are interconnected within the experience described by the interviewee.

Co-occurrences should not be interpreted as causal relationships or as statistical associations, nor do they constitute statistical evidence in themselves. Rather, they should be understood as discursive indicators that require contextual interpretation.

In the case of ATLAS.ti, the software provides both the count of co-occurrences and a co-occurrence coefficient, which is a descriptive index. This coefficient reflects the strength of the discursive relationship rather than statistical significance. Thus, the key idea of co-occurrence analysis is not to count themes, but to examine how themes appear together within the discourse.

6.2. Steps for Co-occurrence Analysis with ATLAS.ti

CAQDAS software enables the generation of tables that display how frequently different codes appear together within the corpus. In ATLAS.ti, these tables can be used to examine relationships between pairs of codes or between groups of categories.

The general procedure can be summarised as follows:

1. Select the codes to be compared.
2. Generate the co-occurrence table within the software.
3. Examine the values indicating how often the codes coincide.
4. Review the corresponding text segments to interpret the observed relationships.

This analysis makes it possible to identify recurrent combinations of categories within the corpus.

To conduct co-occurrence analysis step by step in ATLAS.ti, the procedure is as follows:

1. In the *Analyze* menu, activate the Co-occurrence Analysis option.

2. In the interface, select all the relevant codes to observe co-occurrences. In the example, all available codes have been selected. ATLAS.ti also allows the export of the co-occurrence matrix to Excel for further external analysis.

Figure 9. Co-occurrence matrix

3. If required, the coefficient can be activated (Settings / Show coefficient).

The co-occurrence coefficient used in ATLAS.ti indicates how frequently two codes appear together within the same segments of the corpus. This coefficient ranges from 0 to 1. It is

based on the normalised relationship between co-occurrences and the sum of individual occurrences (it is not a classical statistical coefficient such as Jaccard or Phi). Values close to 0 indicate that the codes rarely appear together, whereas higher values indicate that they tend to co-occur more frequently within the same segments. This indicator allows for the observation of how different themes identified during coding are related.

For each pair of codes, a numerical value is displayed, as shown in Figure 10.

Figure 10. Values in the co-occurrence table

1 (0,20)		
	1 (0,25)	
1 (0,25)	Emotional stress(4) @ Frustration(1)	

A high value indicates a strong discursive relationship, suggesting that the codes tend to appear together. However, as previously noted, this does not imply statistical association or causality. The possible interpretative ranges of the coefficient are presented in Table 3.

Table 3. Interpretative values of the coefficient	
Coefficient	Interpretation
0	Never appear together
0,1 - 0,3	Weak relationship
0,3 – 0,5	Moderate relationship
> 0,5	Strong relationship

Sources: Armborst (2017); Friese (2019); ATLAS.ti (2023).

6.3. How to Identify Thematic Relationships

Co-occurrence analysis makes it possible to identify thematic clusters or patterns of relationships between codes, that is, sets of codes that tend to appear together within the corpus. These clusters may reveal relevant dimensions of the phenomenon under study.

Among the main uses of this type of analysis are the following:

- Detecting relationships between themes within the discourse.
- Identifying emerging analytical dimensions.
- Exploring how different aspects of the phenomenon are articulated.

For example, in studies on professional practice, frequent relationships may emerge between categories such as time management, workload, and emotional stress. This type of pattern suggests that these themes form part of the same dimension of professional experience.

6.4. Interpretation of Thematic Clusters

The interpretation of co-occurrences always requires returning to the original text. Numerical results indicate how frequently two codes appear together, but they do not explain the meaning of that relationship.

For this reason, co-occurrence analysis typically combines two steps:

1. Identification of co-occurrence patterns through software.
2. Interpretative reading of the text segments in which those codes appear.

This procedure makes it possible to examine how specific relationships are constructed within participants' discourse.

For example, it may occur that several fragments of the corpus include the codes *stress*, *fatigue*, and *frustration* within the same discursive context. This co-occurrence would indicate that these are not independent themes; rather, they form a shared emotional cluster and jointly construct the experience of work-related pressure.

Stress – Fatigue – Frustration

A possible interpretative reading could be as follows:

“Stress manifests itself as sustained fatigue and generates frustration when professional expectations cannot be met.”

This interpretation does not emerge automatically; it is constructed through the relationship between codes.

6.5. Limitations of Co-occurrence Analysis

Although co-occurrence analysis can provide valuable insights into the structure of discourse, it is important to recognise its limitations.

In particular, co-occurrences:

- Do not indicate causality between variables.
- Do not represent statistical associations.
- Do not allow for generalisable inferences on their own.

Their primary function is to explore thematic relationships within the corpus and to guide subsequent interpretative analysis. For example, two codes may co-occur because a participant describes a complex situation, rather than because there is a generalisable conceptual association between them.

6.6. Preparation for Structural Analysis of the Corpus

Co-occurrence analysis constitutes an intermediate stage between interpretative qualitative analysis and the structural analysis of the corpus. For the latter, a binary matrix (presence/absence) is typically used, although in some profile-based methods it is also possible to work with frequencies.

Once the relationships between codes have been identified, the coding can be transformed into a data structure that allows for the examination of how categories are distributed across different documents. This process involves constructing analytical matrices that relate codes and documents. Based on these matrices, it is possible to apply various structural analysis techniques, such as:

- Contingency tables
- Chi-square test
- Cramér's V coefficient
- Correspondence analysis

These tools enable the exploration of patterns, associations, and internal structures within the corpus beyond the initial qualitative interpretation.

7. Conversion of Coding into a Dataset

Up to this point, the analysis has focused on the qualitative interpretation of the corpus through coding, frequency analysis, and co-occurrence analysis. One of the objectives of this manual is to demonstrate how the information generated during coding can be reorganised into a data structure that allows for the analysis of global patterns within the corpus using exploratory techniques.

This process involves converting the results of coding into a structured dataset, typically in the form of a matrix that relates documents and codes. Based on this matrix, it becomes possible to analyse the distribution of themes across the corpus and to examine relationships between analytical categories.

7.1. The Code–Document Matrix

The most commonly used structure for this type of analysis is the code–document matrix. In this matrix, rows represent the documents in the corpus, and columns represent the codes used during the coding process.

Each cell in the matrix indicates whether a given code appears in a specific document. In its simplest form, this relationship is represented using binary variables (Table 4):

- **1** indicates the presence of the code in the document.
- **0** indicates its absence.

Table 4. Example of a code–document matrix				
Document	Emotional stress	Workload burden	Lack of resources	Teamwork
Text 1	1	1	1	1
Text 2	1	0	1	0
Text 3	1	1	1	1

This matrix allows for an immediate visualisation of how different categories are distributed across the corpus. This tabular representation forms the basis for all subsequent quantitative analyses.

7.2. Presence versus Frequency

In this type of matrix, it is important to distinguish between the presence of a code and its frequency of occurrence. In many structural analyses, the presence or absence of a code within a document is used rather than the total number of coded segments.

The reason for this is that the number of coded fragments may depend on factors such as the length of the text or the narrative style of the participant. Frequency may therefore be influenced by document length or discursive style. In contrast, presence/absence allows for more homogeneous comparisons across documents. For example, if a code appears at least once in a document, it is recorded as present, regardless of the number of coded segments.

7.3. Construction of the matrix from ATLAS.ti

The code–document matrix can be constructed from tables generated by qualitative data analysis software. In ATLAS.ti, it is possible to export tables that display the relationship between codes and documents.

The general procedure includes the following steps:

1. Generate a table within the software that relates codes and documents.
2. Export the table to a spreadsheet format, such as Excel.
3. Review the structure of the table and select the codes relevant to the analysis.

Afterwards, it is necessary to transform the table values into binary variables indicating the presence or absence of each code. Once this process is completed, the matrix can be used as a dataset for subsequent exploratory analyses.

Figure 11 illustrates how the code–document matrix can be generated in ATLAS.ti. In the settings panel, it is possible to select the option to rotate the table, a function that allows rows and columns to be inverted depending on analytical needs. The table can then be exported and used directly in Excel, or further processed using R, Jamovi, or Python.

Figure 11. Code–document matrix

7.4. Selection of Codes for Analysis

It is not always necessary to include all codes in the analytical matrix. In many cases, it is advisable to select a subset of codes that represent the most relevant dimensions of the phenomenon under study.

This selection can be based on several criteria:

- Theoretical relevance of the category
- Frequency of occurrence in the corpus
- Analytical importance within the study

Selecting a subset of codes helps to avoid matrices that are overly sparse or difficult to interpret.

7.5. Preparation of the Dataset for Statistical Analysis

Once the code–document matrix has been constructed, the next step is to prepare the dataset for analysis using statistical software. Programmes such as Microsoft Excel, Jamovi, R, or Python allow this type of matrix to be analysed using various exploratory techniques.

Among the most commonly used techniques are:

- Contingency tables → Chapter 8
- Tests of association between categorical variables Chapter 8
- Exploratory multivariate analysis → Chapter 9

These techniques make it possible to examine the structure of the corpus from a perspective complementary to qualitative analysis.

The code–document matrix constitutes a key component of the methodological procedure. It enables the examination of how themes are distributed across the corpus and facilitates the exploration of relationships between analytical categories. This type of structural analysis does not replace qualitative interpretation; rather, it complements it by providing an overall view of the patterns present in the data. Quantitative analysis is used here as a tool to explore the structural coherence of the patterns identified during qualitative analysis.

8. Analysis of Associations between Variables

Once the code–document matrix has been constructed, it becomes possible to examine relationships between different analytical categories using exploratory analytical techniques. One of the most commonly used tools for this purpose is the contingency table, which allows the examination of relationships between two categorical variables.

In the context of qualitative analysis, these variables are typically derived from the coding of the corpus. For example, it is possible to analyse the relationship between a specific code and the type of document in which it appears, or between different analytical categories identified during the coding process.

8.1. Contingency Tables

A contingency table displays the joint distribution of two categorical variables. In the analysis of qualitative corpora, it can be used to examine the relationship between the presence of a code and a characteristic of the corpus, such as the type of document.

For instance, if the corpus includes micro-interviews, professional narratives, and focus groups, it is possible to examine whether certain themes appear more frequently in one type of material than in others. A simplified example is shown in Table 5:

Table 5. Simplified example of a contingency table

Document type	Emotional stress present	Emotional stress absent
Micro-interview	3	1
Professional narrative	2	1
Focus group	1	0

This type of table allows for a rapid visualization of how a given theme is distributed across the corpus.

8.1.1. Generation of the Contingency Table

Following this example, the steps to generate a contingency table using ATLAS.ti are outlined below:

- a) In the Analyze menu, select Code–Document Analysis. Choose the relevant codes for the study and select all documents in the corpus. In this example, the following codes are selected: Coordination / teamwork, Decision-making, Emotional exhaustion, Emotional stress, Frustration, Institutional communication, Lack of resources, Professional motivation, Service organisation, Time management, Workload burden, applied to Microinterview_1, 2, and 3.

Figure 12. Code–document selection

- b) Once the table has been generated, the values must be binarised. The aim is not to analyse frequency, but rather the presence or absence of each code in each document (document-level density). To do so, select: **Settings / Binarize**, as shown in Figure 13.

Figure 13. Binarize option in ATLAS.ti

The result is a binarised table, as illustrated in Figure 14.

Figure 14. Binarized data: codes versus documents

		1: Microinter... 7	2: Microinter... 5	3: Microinter... 6	Totals
• ◆ Coordination / teamwork	2	•		•	2
• ◆ Decision-making	2		•	•	2
• ◆ Emotional exhaustion	2	•		•	2
• ◆ Emotional stress	4	•	•	•	3
• ◆ Frustration	1	•			1
• ◆ Institutional communication	1	•			1
• ◆ Lack of resources	3	•	•	•	3
• ◆ Professional motivation	3	•	•	•	3
• ◆ Service organisation	3		•	•	2
• ◆ Time management	4	•	•	•	3
• ◆ Workload burden	2	•			1
Totals		9	6	8	23

c) The next step is to export the table to Excel.

d) The resulting Excel file will display a table similar to the following:

Table 6. Export from Excel (code–document option)

	Microinterview_1	Microinterview_2	Microinterview_3	Total
● Workload	1	0	0	1
● Teamwork	1	0	1	2
● Emotional stress	1	1	1	3
● Lack of resources	1	1	1	3
● Frustration	1	0	0	1
● Time management	1	1	1	3
● Professional motivation	1	1	1	3
● Service organisation	0	1	1	2
Total	7	5	6	18

If we consider **document-level density**, it can be observed that Microinterview_1 contains a greater number of distinct codes and therefore presents a broader thematic profile. Microinterview_2, by contrast, displays a different pattern.

From Table 6, it is also possible to derive a frequency table based on code presence across documents (Table 7):

Table 7. Frequency table based on document occurrence	
Codes (statistical variable)	Number of documents
● Workload	1
● Teamwork	2
● Emotional stress	3
● Lack of resources	3
● Frustration	1
● Time management	3
● Professional motivation	3
● Service organisation	2
Total	

At this point, and for the purposes of statistical analysis, the selected codes are treated as variables.

- e) To work with statistical software (JAMOVI, JASP, R, or Python), it is necessary to reorganise the data so that each document corresponds to a row and each code to a column. An initial step is illustrated in Table 8:

Table 8. Initial structure of the contingency table

	Microinterview_1
● Workload	1
● Teamwork	1
● Emotional stress	1
● Lack of resources	1
● Frustration	1
● Time management	1
● Professional motivation	1
● Service organisation	0
Total	7

Based on this reorganisation, the complete table is constructed (Table 9). It serves as the basis for subsequent analyses (χ^2 , Cramér's V, correspondence analysis):

Table 9. Resulting contingency table

	Workload burden	Teamwork	Emotional stress	Lack of resources	Frustration	Time management	Professional motivation	Service organisation
Microinterview_1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0
Microinterview_2	0	0	1	1	0	1	1	1
Microinterview_3	0	1	1	1	0	1	1	1

In the following video (in Spanish), the organisation of the table is demonstrated: <https://youtu.be/TDFeTOJrlrU>

8.2. Methodological Note on Contingency Tables

Contingency tables can be generated with any number of cases; however, their statistical interpretation depends on sample size. Some conventional and indicative thresholds are as follows:

- With fewer than 10 interviews, results should be considered exploratory or illustrative and interpreted with caution (Agresti 2013; Marshall et al. 2019).
- With between 10 and 20 interviews, the analysis may provide preliminary indications, but interpretation should remain cautious (Braun and Clarke 2006; Mason 2010).
- With larger datasets, statistical tests tend to be more reliable, provided that expected cell frequencies are not too low (Fakis et al. 2014).

When analysing very small numbers of cases (for example, three or four interviews), software may still produce statistics such as χ^2 or Cramér's V; however, these results should be interpreted only as examples of calculation rather than as evidence of real association.

8.3. Chi-square Test

Once the contingency table has been constructed (**Table 9**), statistical calculations can be performed. It is important to note that only variables that vary within the table are relevant for analysis. Variables that do not vary are not informative and should be excluded. In the reduced contingency table (**Table 10**), non-varying variables are highlighted.

Table 10. Contingency table with non-varying values

	Workload burden	Teamwork	Emotional stress	Lack of resources	Professional motivation	Service organisation
Microinterview_1	1	1	1	1	1	0
Microinterview_2	0	0	1	1	1	1
Microinterview_3	0	1	1	1	1	1

To assess whether a relationship exists between the variables represented in a contingency table, the **Chi-square test of independence** is used. This test compares observed values with expected values under the assumption that the variables are independent.

In general terms, the procedure involves comparing:

- **Observed values:** the actual distribution of the data.
- **Expected values:** the distribution that would be obtained if no relationship existed between the variables.

The Chi-square test addresses the following question:

Is the distribution of codes independent of the type of document, or is there a relationship?

The interpretation of the result is based on the p-value obtained:

- $p < 0.05$ suggests a statistically significant association between variables.
- $p \geq 0.05$ indicates that there is insufficient evidence to assert an association.

McHugh (2013) notes that the Chi-square test is particularly suitable for analysing relationships between categorical variables in exploratory studies.

8.3.1. Step-by-step Calculation of Chi-square with JAMOVİ

To calculate Chi-square (χ^2), the software JAMOVİ (<https://www.jamovi.org/>) can be used. The following video <https://youtu.be/Twie3taX4rQ> demonstrates how to load a spreadsheet into JAMOVİ.

Once the contingency table has been created manually and saved in a spreadsheet format (e.g., Microsoft Excel), the following steps should be followed:

1) Verify that all variables to be analysed are integers.

Figure 15. Verification of the variables

2) Select the option for **independent samples**.

Figure 16. Selection of independence test

3) Select the two variables for which the association is to be tested. In the example, **Decision-Making and Frustration** are selected.

Figure 17. Selection of variables

One of the advantages of software such as JAMOVI is that it provides results immediately. In this case, the output indicates that $p > 0.05$ (specifically, 0.083), meaning that there is insufficient evidence to support the existence of an association, as previously explained.

Note: Attention should be paid to the sample size. In this example, $N = 3$ (three documents), which is a very small sample. This represents one of the main limitations of the example. Such small samples mean that the results should be interpreted solely as illustrations of the procedure rather than as substantive empirical findings.

8.4. Effect Size: Cramér's V

The Chi-square test allows for determining whether an association exists between variables, but it does not indicate the strength of that relationship. To estimate the magnitude of the association, **Cramér's V coefficient** is used.

Cramér's V ranges between **0 and 1**, where:

- **0** indicates no association
- **1** indicates a perfect association

In exploratory studies, the following indicative thresholds are commonly used (Afrianti, Pasaribu and Ardy 2024; Cohen 2013; Kearney 2017; Rea and Parker 2014):

Table 11. Indicative values of Cramér’s V

Cramér’s V value	Interpretation
$\approx 0,10$	Weak association
$\approx 0,30$	Moderate association
$\geq 0,50$	Strong association

The values presented in Table 11 should be interpreted with caution (as descriptive indicators), particularly when the number of documents in the corpus is small, as in the present example.

8.4.1. Step-by-step Calculation of Cramér’s V with JAMOVI

To calculate Cramér’s V in JAMOVI, open the **Statistics** options and select **Phi and Cramér’s V**, as shown in the following figure:

Figure 18. Calculation of Cramér’s V using JAMOVI

The screenshot displays the JAMOVI interface for calculating Cramér’s V. On the left, the 'Contingency Tables' dialog box shows 'Decision-making' as the row variable and 'Coordination / teamwork' as the column variable. The 'Statistics' section is expanded, and 'Phi and Cramér's V' is selected. The 'Results' window on the right shows the following contingency table:

Service organisation	Coordination / teamwork		Total
	0	1	
0	0	1	1
1	1	1	2
Total	1	2	3

Below the contingency table, the 'Chi-squared Tests' table shows:

	Value	df	p
χ^2	0.750	1	0.386
N	3		

The 'Nominal' section shows the following results:

	Value
Phi-coefficient	0.500
Cramer's V	0.500

Although Cramér's V yields a value of 0.5, which would conventionally be interpreted as a moderate or strong association, this result **lacks interpretative** validity due to the very small sample size ($N = 3$). The χ^2 test does not provide statistical evidence of association ($p = 0.386$), and the assumptions required for its application are not met. Therefore, although $V = 0.5$ in this example, this value is not interpretable given the extremely small sample size and the non-significant χ^2 result.

8.5. Limitations of Statistical Analysis in Qualitative Corpora

When applying statistical tests to data derived from qualitative coding, several limitations must be considered:

1. Qualitative corpora are often small in size, which reduces statistical power.
2. Expected frequencies in contingency tables may be too low, invalidating the use of the Chi-square test.
3. Cramér's V can be calculated, but it should be interpreted as a descriptive rather than a confirmatory indicator.
4. The primary objective is not statistical inference, but the exploration of the internal structure of the corpus.

Consequently, these analyses should be understood as complements to qualitative interpretation, rather than as substitutes.

When the number of interviews is very small, expected cell frequencies may be insufficient, limiting the reliability of tests such as χ^2 . In such situations, measures of association such as Cramér's V can still be calculated, but they must be interpreted with caution and primarily as descriptive indicators rather than as evidence of robust statistical association (Field 2024; Field 2026).

For this reason, results obtained through statistical tests should be interpreted mainly as exploratory indicators that help examine the structural coherence of patterns identified during qualitative analysis. Statistical tests should therefore be understood as complementary tools that support qualitative interpretation, rather than replacing it.

8.6. Preparation for the Visualisation of Patterns

Contingency tables and tests of association allow relationships between variables to be examined analytically. However, as the number of codes or documents increases, these tables may become difficult to interpret. For this reason, many studies employ data visualisation techniques to represent graphically the relationships between documents and analytical categories. One of the most widely used techniques for this purpose is correspondence analysis, which allows the structure of a contingency table to be represented in a two-dimensional space where the following can be observed:

- proximities between documents,
- relationships between codes,
- thematic groupings.

9. Visualisation of Discursive Patterns: Correspondence Analysis

When working with coded qualitative corpora, a common challenge arises from the simultaneous presence of multiple codes and multiple documents. As the number of analytical categories and units of analysis increases, exploring the relationships between them becomes more complex.

Contingency tables allow for the organisation of data and the calculation of possible associations between variables (codes). However, they present certain interpretative limitations: when the number of codes is high, tables may become difficult to read and do not easily reveal global patterns within the corpus. Moreover, although they display relationships between variables, these relationships are not always intuitively visible.

For this reason, it is useful to complement the analysis with **visual representations**. Visualisations synthesise information, facilitate the interpretation of associations, and enable the identification of patterns that may not be evident in numerical tables.

Among the available visualisation techniques, one of the most widely used is **correspondence analysis**, which allows for the graphical representation of relationships between analytical categories and corpus documents. It is an exploratory statistical method specifically designed to analyse contingency tables. Its objective is to represent, in a two-dimensional space, the relationship between rows and columns of the data table, showing patterns of proximity between the analysed categories (Greenacre 2017; Qi et al. 2024; Žlahtič et al. 2024). The structural analysis techniques employed are exploratory in nature, and their purpose is to identify relational patterns within the corpus, which must subsequently be interpreted through contextualised reading of the texts.

In constructing the contingency table, both binary values (presence/absence) and **frequency counts** may be used. For association tests such as χ^2 , binary variables are recommended; however, for correspondence analysis, **frequency tables** are generally more appropriate, as the method is based on comparing distribution profiles of rows and columns (Greenacre 2017; Kamalja, Kiran and Vijair 2017; Qi et al. 2024).

9.1 Correspondence Analysis

Correspondence analysis is based on a contingency table that captures the distribution of categories across two variables. It is an **exploratory and descriptive** technique (Greenacre 2017). From this table, the method generates a geometric representation in a two-dimensional plane, where the categories represented in rows and columns appear as points.

This representation facilitates the identification of **proximities** between categories and documents. In the analysis of qualitative corpora, it is common that:

- **Rows** represent the **documents** in the corpus.
- **Columns** represent the **analytical categories or codes** derived from coding.

In this way, the analysis allows for identifying which codes are closer to particular documents, as well as thematic groupings and similarities between coding profiles. In this representation (Figure 19):

- **Points that appear close** to each other indicate a stronger relationship between the represented categories or documents.
- **Points that are further apart** indicate weaker relationships or distinct profile

Figure 19. Example of a correspondence analysis *biplot*

The graph shows which documents and categories are more closely related. The shorter the distance between two points in the factorial map, the stronger their structural association. This representation allows for identifying global patterns and potential thematic groupings within the corpus.

Thus, correspondence analysis enables the identification of structural patterns and potential groupings within the corpus based on the proximity between documents and categories in the factorial map. In general terms, the smaller the distance between points, the stronger the association between the represented elements.

9.2. Interpretation of Two-dimensional Maps

Correspondence analysis (CA) transforms a **contingency table** into a **visual map**. Instead of observing only numerical values, the method represents information in a plane where points correspond to elements of the table:

- Some points correspond to **documents** (typically shown in blue).
- Other points correspond to **categories or codes** (typically shown in red).

The position of these points is not arbitrary. The algorithm places them in the map so that **distances reflect patterns of association present in the original table**.

In this way, correspondence analysis enables the transition **from a numerical table to a graphical representation** that facilitates the interpretation of relationships between documents and categories. The resulting graph (Figure 20) is referred to as a *biplot*, as it simultaneously displays two types of elements.

In the case of a quantified qualitative corpus:

Rows (in blue)

Represent **documents or interviews**.

Each blue point corresponds to a specific document in the corpus.

Columns (in red)

Represent variables (codes) or **analytical categories**.

Each red point corresponds to a category derived from the coding process.

The map allows for observing how documents and categories are related within the corpus.

Figure 20. Explanatory biplot including all document groups

9.2.1. Rule for Interpreting the Map

The basic rule for interpretation is straightforward:

- The closer two points are, the stronger their structural association.

This implies that:

- A document located near a code tends to contain proportionally more segments associated with that code.
- Two codes that are close to each other tend to appear in similar documents.
- Documents that are close to one another exhibit similar coding profiles.

Conversely, when two points are far apart, their profiles differ. It is important to note that this analysis **does not imply causality**. The map only represents structural proximity within the corpus.

9.2.2. What Do the Axes Represent?

The map (Figure 21) is organised along two axes:

- **Dimension 1 (horizontal)**
- **Dimension 2 (vertical)**

Each dimension represents a **principal direction of variation in the data**.

In the example shown:

Dimension 1 (70.6%)

- Explains 70.6% of the variation observed in the table.
- This means that most differences between documents are structured along this axis.

Dimension 2 (29.4%)

- Explains the remaining 29.4%.
- It represents a secondary pattern of differentiation within the corpus.

When the combined contribution of these two dimensions is high (e.g., above 60%), the map is generally considered visually reliable for interpreting overall patterns.

Figure 21. Explanatory biplot of the axes

9.2.3. Step-by-step Reading of the Map

A simple way to interpret a *biplot* is to follow three steps.

Step 1: Observe proximities

Identify which documents are located close to which categories. If a document is close to a category, that category has relatively greater weight in that document.

Step 2: Observe groupings

Detect whether there are:

- Clusters of documents
- Groups of related codes

These groupings may indicate similar discursive profiles or shared thematic patterns.

Step 3: Interpret the axes

The axes do not have an intrinsic meaning; their interpretation depends on **the distribution of points across the map.**

9.3. Combined Use of Different Types of Documents

In the example presented, different types of materials have been analysed jointly (see Appendix): *focus groups*, micro-interviews, and professional narratives. Although these documents originate from different contexts, all have been coded using **the same codebook.**

This aspect is methodologically essential. Correspondence analysis does not compare documents based on their type or format, but on **their coding profile**, that is, the distribution of categories within each document.

When all materials are coded using the same system of categories, it is possible to construct a single contingency table in which:

- Rows represent **documents, regardless of their type.**

- **Columns represent analytical categories or codes.**

In this way, the analysis allows for examining how themes or categories are distributed across the entire corpus.

9.3.1. Implications for Interpretation

By representing all documents within the same factorial map, the analysis enables the identification of similarities and differences between them.

For example:

- Some **focus groups** may be located close to specific categories.
- Some **micro-interviews** may be associated with different themes.
- Certain documents may exhibit more **mixed or intermediate thematic profiles**, appearing in central areas of the map.

Correspondence analysis does not compare document types per se, but rather **how categories are distributed within each document.**

Methodological Note

This type of analysis is only possible when **all materials share the same coding system.**

If documents had been coded using different categories, it would not be possible to construct a common contingency table or to apply correspondence analysis.

9.4. Step-by-step: From ATLAS.ti to Correspondence Analysis Visualisation

In a similar manner to the procedure followed for the Chi-square (χ^2) test and Cramér's V, all documents in the corpus are incorporated into the correspondence analysis. In this case, all variables are selected, as they may be represented in some documents. This approach is appropriate as long as all materials share the same coding system.

a) In ATLAS.ti: Go to *Analyze / Code–Document Analysis / Focus Group*.

Figure 22. Code–document analysis in ATLAS.ti

b) Export the generated table to Excel.

c) The same procedure should be applied to the professional narratives and micro-interviews.

d) Subsequently, the full contingency table is constructed manually, integrating all documents and all variables (codes) to be analysed.

The resulting table will contain binary values (1 = code present, 0 = code absent).

Before performing correspondence analysis, it is advisable to review the contingency table. Columns that contain only **zero** values can be removed, as they do not contribute **any information** to the analysis. Similarly, variables that take the same value across all documents do not help to differentiate row profiles and are therefore usually excluded in order to simplify the table and facilitate interpretation of the factorial map. Table 12 presents the complete contingency matrix used to explore the thematic structure of the corpus and to prepare the correspondence analysis.

Document	Healthcare setting	Coordination / teamwork	Decision-making	Emotional exhaustion	Emotional stress	Frustration	Institutional communication	Professional experience	Lack of resources	Professional motivation	Service organisation	Time management	Workload burden
Microinterview_1	0	1	0	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	0	1	1
Microinterview_2	0	0	1	0	1	0	0	0	1	1	1	1	0
Microinterview_3	0	1	1	1	1	0	0	0	1	1	1	1	0
Professional_narrative_1	0	1	1	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0
Professiona_Narrative_2	0	0	1	0	0	1	0	0	1	0	0	0	0
Focus_Group	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	0

Table 12. Complete Contingency Matrix

Document	Coordination / teamwork	Decision-making	Emotional exhaustion	Emotional stress	Frustration	Institutional communication	Lack of resources	Professional motivation	Service organisation	Time management	Workload burden
Microinterview_1	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	1
Microinterview_2	0	1	0	1	0	0	1	1	1	1	0
Microinterview_3	1	1	1	1	0	0	1	1	1	1	0
Professional_narrative_1	1	1	1	1	0	0	0	0	1	0	0
Professiona_Narrative_2	0	1	0	0	1	0	1	0	0	0	0
Focus_Group	0	0	0	1	0	0	1	1	0	0	0

Once the contingency tables have been constructed, JAMOVI can be used to load the Excel spreadsheet and perform correspondence analysis, as illustrated in Figures 23, 24, and 25.

Figure 23. Selection of the SnowCluster module in JAMOVI and Correspondence Analysis option

Figure 24. Selection of variables and visualisation of the biplot in correspondence analysis

Figure 25. Interpretation of correspondence analysis

Figure 25 illustrates how the structure of the corpus can be visualised and how distinct thematic patterns between documents and analytical categories can be identified. The biplot shows the joint distribution of documents and codes in a two-dimensional space, where the first two dimensions explain 96.1% of the variability in the corpus (Dim1 = 74.7%; Dim2 = 21.4%). This representation allows for identifying associations between the analysed documents and the coded themes.

Along the horizontal axis (Dim1), a distinction can be observed between, on the right-hand side, elements related to **Decision-making**, **Service organisation** and the **Professional narratives**, and, on the left-hand side, elements linked to emotional stress, professional motivation and the **focus group**, together with several **microinterviews**. This suggests a

differentiation between more strategic or organisational aspects and more experiential or affective dimensions of professional practice.

The vertical axis (Dim2) introduces a second interpretative dimension that differentiates between organisational aspects, such as **Service organisation** (upper part), and elements associated with decision-making and certain **Professional narratives** (lower part). This axis provides an additional layer for interpreting how themes are distributed across the corpus.

The proximity between documents and codes allows for identifying specific relationships within the corpus. For instance, `Professional_narrative_1` is positioned close to **Service organisation**, while `Professional_narrative_2` is strongly associated with decision-making. In contrast, the focus group and several **microinterviews** are located nearer to emotional stress and professional motivation, suggesting differences in the thematic structure across the types of documents analysed.

9.5 Identification of Discursive Profiles and Interpretation of the Factorial Map

Correspondence analysis enables the simultaneous visualisation of the distribution of **documents and analytical categories** within the corpus, based on the code–document matrix generated during the coding process. This technique, widely used in the exploratory analysis of categorical data (Benzécri 1973; Lebart, Salem and Berry 1998), transforms the contingency table into a **factorial map** in which each element is represented as a point. The proximity between points reflects the similarity between their coding profiles (Greenacre 2017).

Two types of elements are represented in this map:

- **Documents (blue points):** each document or interview appears as a point whose position depends on its pattern of coded categories.
- **Categories or codes (red points):** each analytical category is also represented as a point, positioned according to the documents in which it appears.

The distribution of points across the plane allows for **identifying discursive profiles**, that is, groups of documents that share similar thematic patterns. It also facilitates the

detection of **associations between categories**, particularly when several codes systematically appear within the same documents.

When a document is located close to a code, this indicates that the theme is relatively more prominent in that text compared to others in the corpus. The results of the analysis are typically presented in a graph known as a **biplot** (Figures 20, 21, and 22), where the axes represent the two principal dimensions of variation in the table. Each dimension accounts for a proportion of the total variability. **Dimension 1** usually captures most of the differences between documents and categories, while **Dimension 2** represents a complementary axis of differentiation (Greenacre 2017).

The interpretation of the factorial map is based on three fundamental principles:

1. **Proximity between categories**

Categories that are located close to one another tend to appear in the same documents, **indicating similar coding profiles**. For example, codes related to workload and emotional stress may cluster together if they frequently co-occur in the corpus.

2. **Proximity between documents**

Documents that are close together share similar themes or discursive configurations. This makes it possible to identify **subsets of interviews** or texts with comparable thematic profiles.

3. **Relationship between documents and codes**

The proximity between a document and a code indicates that the theme is particularly relevant in that text. If several documents are located near the same code, this may indicate a **shared thematic core**.

The two-dimensional representation of the map is a **simplification** of the actual data structure. Relative positions should be interpreted with caution and always in relation to the original corpus (interviews, narratives, or focus groups). As noted by Lebart, Salem, and Berry (1998), correspondence analysis is fundamentally an exploratory tool: it reveals **latent structures** in the data but does not establish causal relationships.

Overall, this technique allows researchers to:

- identify discursive profiles within the corpus,
- detect groupings of documents with similar thematic configurations,
- observe relationships and distances between analytical categories, and
- obtain an intuitive and global view of the structure of the corpus.

For these reasons, correspondence analysis constitutes a particularly valuable tool in the study of quantified qualitative corpora, as it complements interpretative discourse analysis with a **geometric representation** of relationships between documents and categories (Greenacre 2017).

9.6. Usefulness of Correspondence Analysis in Corpus Exploration and Methodological Limitations

Correspondence analysis is particularly useful for exploring the **internal structure** of a quantified qualitative corpus. Based on the code–document matrix, this technique enables the representation of relationships between documents and categories in a two-dimensional space, facilitating the identification of patterns that are not always evident through linear reading of the corpus or simple inspection of numerical tables (Benzécri 1973; Lebart, Salem and Berry 1998).

Among the main applications of correspondence analysis are the following:

- **Identification of discursive profiles:** the factorial map allows for observing which documents share similar thematic patterns, facilitating the detection of recurrent discursive configurations within the corpus.
- **Detection of document groupings:** documents located close to each other in the plane tend to exhibit comparable coding profiles, which may indicate discursive affinities or shared experiences.
- **Visualization of relationships between analytical categories:** codes that tend to co-occur in the same documents are usually positioned close to one another, revealing potential thematic links within the discourse.

- **Preliminary exploration prior to qualitative interpretation:** the map provides a visual synthesis that guides subsequent interpretative reading, helping to focus attention on the most relevant themes or contrasts between documents.

In this way, correspondence analysis functions as a technique for **structural exploration of the corpus**, offering a global representation of the relationships between documents and categories that complements in-depth qualitative analysis (Greenacre 2017). This type of visualisation is particularly valuable in studies involving numerous codes or multiple types of documents, where relationships may be difficult to discern through contingency tables alone.

However, as an exploratory technique, correspondence analysis presents several **methodological limitations** that must be taken into account:

- The technique **does not establish causal relationships**, but only associations based on the structure of the data table.
- The graphical representation depends on the specific configuration of the matrix: variations in code selection, the presence of low-frequency categories, or the method of binarising the data may alter the position of points in the map.
- The two-dimensional representation is a **simplification** of a potentially more complex geometric structure, meaning that part of the information is always lost outside the represented plane (Lebart, Salem and Berry 1998).
- It requires that all documents share the same coding system to generate a comparable and stable table.

Thus, the results of correspondence analysis should be interpreted as a complementary exploratory tool that guides qualitative reading of the corpus, rather than replacing contextualised interpretation of the texts. The factorial map enables the visualisation of associations and general patterns, but its interpretation must always be conducted in dialogue with the original documents and the coding decisions adopted during the analysis.

10. Reliability of Coding: Intercoder Agreement and Krippendorff's Alpha

In qualitative studies that employ systematic coding procedures, one of the most important methodological aspects is the **reliability of the coding process** (Goyanes and Piñeiro-Naval 2024). Reliability refers to the extent to which different researchers apply the same codes consistently when analysing the same dataset (Hayes and Krippendorff 2007; Krippendorff 2011).

When multiple coders participate in the analysis, it is necessary to verify that the coding system is applied coherently. If different researchers assign different codes to the same text segments, the results of the analysis may be affected by coder subjectivity.

For this reason, many qualitative studies incorporate procedures to **assess intercoder agreement**, particularly when the analysis includes systematic or quantifiable elements.

10.1. Importance of Intercoder Agreement

Intercoder agreement is an indicator of the clarity and operability of the coding system. A high level of agreement suggests that analytical categories are well defined, clearly delimited, and can be applied consistently across the corpus.

Conversely, a low level of agreement may indicate problems in the design of the coding system, such as:

- Ambiguous category definitions
- Conceptual overlap between codes
- Unclear application criteria

In such cases, it is usually necessary to revise the coding system and refine category definitions before continuing the analysis.

10.2. Measures of Reliability in Qualitative Analysis

Several statistical indicators can be used to assess intercoder agreement. Among the most widely known are:

- Cohen’s kappa, for two coders
- Fleiss’ kappa, for more than two coders
- Krippendorff’s alpha, applicable with multiple coders and different types of data

Among these, Krippendorff’s alpha has become one of the most widely used measures in content analysis, due to its flexibility and applicability to different data types and multiple coders (Krippendorff 2018).

10.3. Krippendorff’s Alpha

Krippendorff’s alpha measures the level of agreement between coders while accounting for agreement occurring by chance. The coefficient ranges between 0 and 1, where:

1 indicates perfect agreement
0 indicates no agreement beyond chance

Krippendorff (2019) proposes the following indicative thresholds:

Alpha value	Interpretation
≥ 0,80	High agreement
0,67 – 0,79	Acceptable agreement in exploratory studies
< 0,67	Insufficient agreement

These values should be interpreted in light of the study context, the nature of the data, and the complexity of the coding system. In studies involving high conceptual complexity or subtle categories, it may be necessary to revise and refine the codebook before proceeding.

10.4 Step-by-step Calculation of Krippendorff’s Alpha with ATLAS.ti

Calculating Krippendorff’s alpha requires comparing coding decisions made by different researchers on the same set of text segments. A minimum of two coders is required. In this example, a third person acts as coordinator (Figure 26).

Figure 26. Workflow using CAQDAS software (ATLAS.ti, NVivo)

- 1) Select and read a sample of the corpus. Typically, this represents 10% of the corpus (Álvarez-Cueva et al. 2021; Ruiz et al. 2024), although some studies use up to 20% (Ortega-Mohedano and Galhardi 2013; Goyanes and Piñeiro-Naval 2024).
- 2) Jointly decide which codes will be used. This step may involve several meetings to reach consensus, depending on corpus size.
- 3) The coordinator creates a project in ATLAS.ti, including documents and the codebook.
- 4) Since ATLAS.ti identifies users by name, no further configuration is required.

In the example, “CODER A” and “CODER B” have been created for pedagogical purposes; however, this is not strictly necessary. The coordinator exports the project without coding and sends it to the two coders. To do so, the project must be exported, as shown in the following figures (Figures 27 and 28).

Figure 27. Exporting a project package in ATLAS.ti

Figure 28. Export for coder B

1. The two analysts code the material independently and in parallel.
2. **Return of the coded project**

Once they have completed the coding, they send the project back to the coordinator by exporting it from ATLAS.ti (Figures 27 and 28), following a procedure similar to that carried out by the coordinator.

3. Merging of projects

The coordinator then merges the two coded projects into the original project (Figure 29).

In the case of ATLAS.ti, the following interface will be displayed:

Figure 29. Merging projects in ATLAS.ti

Once the import process is completed, ATLAS.ti displays a summary of the merged content. In ATLAS.ti, it is possible to verify that both coders have been added as users of the project (Figure 30).

Figure 30. List of users in ATLAS.ti

1) Activating intercoder analysis mode

Go to Analyze / Activate Intercoder Agreement Mode (Figure 31).

Figure 31. Activation of intercoder agreement mode in ATLAS.ti

2) Calculation of Krippendorff's alpha through the following steps (Figures 33–36)

Figure 32. Selection of coders for the analysis

Select the text(s) to be compared, as shown in the following figure:

Figure 33. Selection of documents for analysis in ATLAS.ti

Once the texts have been selected, add the codes to be analysed:

Figure 34. Selection of codes for analysis in ATLAS.ti

After selecting the codes, a screen will appear displaying the texts coded by both analysts (coders). In this interface, it is possible to observe where there is agreement and where discrepancies occur. In Figure 36, agreements between *Coder_A* and *Coder_B* can be identified.

Figure 35. Execution of Krippendorff's analysis in ATLAS.ti

To obtain Krippendorff's alpha in ATLAS.ti, access the Measure % button and select Krippendorff's alpha, as shown in Figure 36:

Figure 36. Calculation of Krippendorff's alpha

As previously mentioned, the interpretation of Krippendorff's alpha values is as follows:

≥ 0.80	→	strong agreement
0.67–0.79	→	acceptable with caution
< 0.67	→	problematic

If the value is below 0.60, it is recommended to manually review which segments have been coded differently by the coders, as this indicates a high level of disagreement. Krippendorff's alpha can also be calculated using specific functions in software such as R, SPSS, or Python (Field 2026).

10.5. Interpretation of Results

The value obtained through Krippendorff's alpha makes it possible to evaluate the consistency of the coding process among multiple evaluators.

1. A high level of agreement ($\alpha \geq 0.80$) indicates that the coding system is applied consistently and that the results of the analysis can be considered methodologically robust.
2. A value ($0.67 \leq \alpha < 0.80$) may be considered acceptable in exploratory studies, although it requires caution.
3. By contrast, if the coefficient is low ($\alpha < 0.67$), it is advisable to revise the coding system and clarify the definitions of categories before continuing the analysis (Krippendorff 2019).

As Krippendorff (2018) notes, the aim of content analysis is not merely to obtain numerical agreement between coders, but to develop coherent interpretations of the phenomenon under study. The assessment of intercoder agreement should be understood as a methodological complement that contributes to improving transparency and consistency in the analytical process.

In some qualitative studies, particularly those involving a single analyst—as is often the case in doctoral theses—the calculation of intercoder agreement is not always possible. In such cases, a detailed description of the coding process becomes a fundamental strategy to ensure the credibility of the analysis and methodological transparency. This description should include the following elements:

- the development of the codebook,
- the criteria used to assign categories,
- the analytical decisions made during the process.

This documentation forms the basis for ensuring the credibility and methodological transparency of the analysis.

11. Integration of Results: Interpretation of the Corpus

The previous stages have made it possible to analyse the corpus from different methodological perspectives. First, the coding process **structured the corpus** through analytical categories. Subsequently, the exploration of frequencies and **co-occurrences** facilitated the identification of recurrent themes and relationships between codes. Finally, the construction of **analytical matrices** enabled the application of exploratory techniques to examine the structure of the corpus.

The objective of this section is to explain how to integrate the results obtained through these different analytical strategies and how to interpret **the patterns** identified in the data.

11.1 Methodological Triangulation

The combination of different analytical techniques can be understood as a form of methodological triangulation. In social research, triangulation consists of using multiple approaches or methods to examine the same phenomenon in order to enhance the robustness of the results.

In the context of qualitative analysis, triangulation allows for combining:

- Discourse interpretation (interpretative qualitative analysis)
- Systematic exploration of the corpus (frequencies, co-occurrences, matrices)
- Structural analysis of coded data (contingency tables and correspondence analysis)

Creswell and Plano Clark (2018) note that this type of integration is characteristic of **mixed methods** approaches, in which qualitative and quantitative techniques are used in a complementary manner.

11.2 Integration of Qualitative and Structural Results

In the procedure presented in this manual, corpus interpretation is based on the integration of three analytical levels.

First level: interpretative qualitative analysis

This corresponds to the process of reading the corpus and identifying analytical categories through coding. Qualitative interpretation allows for understanding the meaning of discourse and situating it within its social context.

Second level: descriptive exploration of the corpus

At this stage, **code frequencies**, the distribution of categories across documents, and co-occurrences between themes are analysed. This analysis enables the identification of initial **patterns** and guides the interpretation of the corpus.

Third level: structural analysis

Structural analysis is based on analytical matrices and exploratory techniques used to examine the organisation of the corpus:

1. Contingency tables
2. Chi-square test (χ^2)
3. Cramér's V
4. Correspondence analysis

From the code–document matrix, contingency tables and correspondence analysis allow for identifying relationships between categories and detecting thematic configurations within the data.

The combination of these three levels—interpretative qualitative analysis, descriptive exploration, and structural analysis—makes it possible to examine the corpus from multiple analytical perspectives and to deepen the understanding of patterns present in the discourse.

Figure 37. Three-level analytical model

11.3 Interpretation of Discursive Patterns

The integration of results should focus on identifying discursive patterns within the corpus. These patterns may manifest in different ways, for example:

- Recurrent themes appearing across different documents
- Frequent relationships between specific analytical categories
- Groupings of documents that share similar thematic configurations

Structural analysis allows these relationships to be visualised through maps and graphical representations. However, the interpretation of these patterns always requires returning to the original corpus. The factorial map identifies proximities, but only the contextualised reading of texts allows for understanding:

- how themes are articulated,
- in which contexts they appear,
- what meanings participants attribute to them.

Therefore, the final interpretation must integrate:

- what is observed in the visualisations,
- what is identified through frequencies and co-occurrences, and
- what is directly read in the discourse.

11.4 Limitations of the Methodological Approach

The procedure presented in this manual enables the examination of qualitative corpora through different analytical techniques. However, several limitations should be acknowledged. First, structural analyses depend on the decisions made during the **coding process**. An inadequate coding system may affect the results obtained in subsequent stages.

Second, the exploratory techniques used in this manual are not designed to produce generalisable inferences. Their purpose is to examine the internal organisation of the corpus and to **detect and explore patterns** within the analysed data. Third, results must always be interpreted within the specific **context** of the study.

11.5. From Analysis to Knowledge

Despite these limitations, the combination of qualitative analysis and structural exploration can provide a more comprehensive understanding of the phenomenon under study. This approach enables the examination of both the content of discourse, the internal organisation of themes within the corpus, and the relational structure of the corpus.

Structural analysis does not replace qualitative interpretation; rather, it provides additional tools to explore data and identify patterns that may enrich the interpretation of the corpus.

12. Conclusions

Qualitative analysis constitutes a fundamental tool for understanding complex social phenomena through the interpretation of discourse, experiences, and professional practices. In the social sciences, this type of analysis allows for examining how individuals construct meanings in specific contexts and how these meanings are articulated within particular institutional or professional frameworks.

This manual has presented a methodological procedure that connects different stages of qualitative analysis in order to systematically examine the structure of a textual corpus. The process begins with qualitative coding, in which a coding system is developed to organise the corpus and represent the relevant dimensions of the phenomenon under study. Conceptual clarity of categories and consistency in their application are essential elements for ensuring the quality of the analysis.

Once coding has been completed, an initial exploration of the corpus can be conducted through frequency analysis and the identification of co-occurrences between codes. These tools facilitate the detection of recurrent themes and allow for observing how different dimensions of the phenomenon are related within participants' discourse. Based on this information, an analytical matrix is constructed linking documents and codes, forming the basis for the application of exploratory analytical techniques.

On this matrix, tools such as contingency tables, the Chi-square test, and Cramér's V coefficient can be applied to examine relationships between categorical variables derived from coding. These techniques provide a structural view of the corpus that complements traditional qualitative interpretation.

In addition to these association tests, the manual has introduced visualization and multivariate exploratory techniques, particularly correspondence analysis. This technique enables the graphical representation of relationships between documents and analytical categories, identifying thematic groupings and discursive configurations that may not be evident through textual inspection alone. Another important methodological aspect addressed in this manual is the reliability of the coding process. The evaluation of intercoder agreement, through indicators such as Krippendorff's alpha, allows for

assessing consistency in the application of the coding system and strengthens the methodological rigour of the analysis.

The combination of all these analytical strategies constitutes a form of methodological triangulation, integrating different techniques to examine the corpus from multiple perspectives. This approach allows for articulating qualitative interpretation of discourse with structural analysis of coded data. The methodological procedure presented has been illustrated through an applied case in the field of nursing, although the methods described can be applied to other types of corpora in the social sciences, including interviews, focus groups, institutional documents, or professional narratives.

This manual proposes an approach that connects three fundamental dimensions of qualitative analysis:

1. the interpretation of discourse,
2. the systematisation of the analytical process, and
3. the structural exploration of the corpus.

The integration of these dimensions facilitates the identification of analytical patterns within the data and contributes to improving the transparency of the research process. The objective of this methodological procedure is to provide researchers with a clear and replicable guide that enables the transition from qualitative discourse analysis to the identification of thematic structures within the analysed corpus. In this way, the proposed approach contributes to expanding the possibilities of qualitative analysis in contemporary social research.

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APPENDIX

Texts used for illustrative purposes

Text 1 – Micro-interview

I work as a nurse in a hospital unit with a high patient turnover. The workload pressure is constant and, on many occasions, the time available conditions the quality of care we can provide. I try to maintain a person-centred approach, but this is not always easy when there is a shortage of staff and multiple tasks to manage simultaneously.

One of the main difficulties is communication with patients and their families, especially in situations of stress or uncertainty. At times, I feel frustrated at not being able to dedicate the time I consider necessary to explain procedures or listen to concerns.

On a personal level, this context generates emotional fatigue, although it has also helped me develop strategies to prioritise tasks and work as part of a team. I consider peer support to be essential in managing the daily workload. Despite the challenges, I continue to find meaning in my work when I perceive that care has a positive impact on patient well-being.

Text 2 – Micro-interview

My experience as a nurse in primary care differs from hospital settings, although it is no less complex. The continuous follow-up of patients allows for the development of trust-based relationships, but it also involves managing long-term expectations.

One of the most frequent challenges is the lack of resources, both material and temporal. This often requires making quick decisions and, at times, adapting protocols to the realities of the centre. I am concerned that these adaptations are not always understood at higher management levels.

Emotionally, prolonged contact with certain patients can be demanding, particularly in cases of chronic conditions or social vulnerability. Nevertheless, I value the professional autonomy and the possibility of intervening from a more preventive and community-oriented perspective..

Text 3 – Micro-interview

I have been working as a nurse in a primary care centre for approximately eight years. My daily work combines direct patient care, follow-up of chronic patients, and administrative tasks that often take more time than desired.

One of the main issues is time management. Despite efforts to organise appointments, unexpected demands are frequent and disrupt planning. This generates a sense of pressure and makes it difficult to maintain high-quality care.

To manage this, I prioritise urgent cases and rely on the team whenever possible. Emotionally, there are days of fatigue, but also moments of satisfaction when follow-up leads to positive outcomes.

In general, I value the ongoing relationship with patients, although I believe that better organisation and additional resources would greatly facilitate daily work.

Text 4 – Professional Practice Narrative

During an afternoon shift in the hospital unit, several discharges coincided with two emergency admissions. Rapid task reorganisation was essential in order to attend to all patients.

In this context, difficulties arose in coordinating with other professionals and accessing certain material resources. Some decisions had to be made with limited information and under pressure.

Despite these tensions, teamwork made it possible to resolve the situation without serious incidents. At the end of the shift, there was a sense of exhaustion, but also of having responded appropriately to a complex situation.

Text 5 – Professional Practice Narrative

As a lead nurse in a unit, part of my role involves coordinating shifts and managing incidents. On a recent occasion, an unexpected absence required the redistribution of tasks among the team.

This decision caused discomfort among some colleagues, who perceived an additional workload. I attempted to explain the criteria used, although not all decisions were well received.

The situation highlighted the importance of communication and recognition of the team's efforts. It also revealed organisational limitations that extend beyond the clinical setting.

Text 6 – Focus Group

Participant 1: During many shifts, I feel that we are constantly working at the limit, with no margin for unexpected situations.

Participant 2: I think the problem is not only the workload, but also how it is organised. Tasks could sometimes be distributed more effectively.

Participant 3: I agree, but I also notice a lack of support from management. Some decisions are made without an understanding of the realities of the service.